

CULTURAL PERSPECTIVE OF MUNDARI TRIBAL COMMUNITY : A SOCIO-ECONOMICAL OVERVIEW

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Abstract

Munda Community is an austroasiatic talking ethnic gathering of india. they overwhelmingly communicate in the mundari language as their local language, which has a place with the munda subgroup of austroasiatic dialects of seven blocks under north 24 paraganas in west Bengal on Mundari tribal groups of **Bagdah , Bongaon , Giaghata , Swarupnagar , Minakhan , Sandeshkhali –II , and Hingaljanj**. In seven blocks only 1200 mundari family has been taken for survey. in this research of “**Cultural Perspective Of Mundari Tribal Community : A Socio-Economical Overview**” using , scale of tribal conflict data collection questionnaire by information collected in this form as per national democratic institute is used for data analysis. “*Exclusive Property Of The National Democratic Institute*” May-2013 , **Scale Of Indian Human Development Survey – II** as per national council of applied economic research (NCAER) is used for data collection and analysis . “*National Council Of Applied Economic Research 08 December 2020*” And **Scale Of Self Made Standarized Questionnaire** is used for data collection (**3 Point Likert Scale**) is applied for data analysis and explanation.as per result “**The Scheduled Tribes**”, which serves the purpose of designating certain mundaari communities, where membership is acquired by birth, for the benefits that the government provides them with the explicit aim of bringing them as par with the other communities of the block & countryside.

Key Words : 1. **Cultural Perspective** 2. **Mundari Sub-Caste** 3. **Socio-Economical Overview** 4. **Social Participation** 5. **Health And Medical Drawbacks** 6. **Agro-Economical Crisis** 7. **Austroasiatic Vernaculars**

Introduction

The clans of India is around 8.6% of the all out Indian populace (Enumeration, 2011). Despite the fact that they have forever been outlined from the standard of Indian populace through their physical and social qualities, being a piece of this country they merit consideration and care at standard with the remainder of the populace. But, since of disconnection and social separation over years, they have been denied of the essential training, abilities, advancement and development of the cutting edge world. The Munda

people group is an Austroasiatic talking ethnic social event of India. They predominantly impart in the Mundari language as their neighborhood language, which has a spot with the Munda subgroup of Austroasiatic vernaculars. Dalton ,Edward Tuite. (2004). 'Enchanting Ethnology of Bengal' is an undeniable work organized which relies upon various races and factions, especially those for the most part called locals, as consumed by the maker. He has assembled different families under nine orders. The Munda are found in the northern areas of east India pressed in the domains of Jharkhand, Odisha, West Bengal and Assam, they are also found in the Rangpur division of Bangladesh. Mundas were the unprivileged and manhandled neighborhood the English rule. They needed to pay rents and work as supported specialists to the zamindars.

Objectives Of Study

1. To Know The Problems Of Social Participation Of Mundari Tribal Groups Of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal
2. To know the causes of health and medical drawbacks of mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal
3. To know the causes of agro-economical crisis of mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal

Hypothesis Of Study

H₀₁ Social participation has no impact on Mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal

H₀₂ There is no relation between health and medical drawback and development of mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal

H₀₃ There is no relation between Agro-economical Crisis and Social Status of mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal

Review Of Literature

Moseley, Malcolm J. (2003), Written in the dated custom this piece attempts to figure out what can be made of the traditional development in managing issues of development combination and improvement first in a shut and some time later in an open economy. **Otsuka, Keijiro. 2009**, there is a lot of interest in destitution decline, there are not very many settled upon methods of reasoning to diminish franticness genuinely. Rowley, Thomas D., ed. (1996), Rural development has regularly centered around the exploitation of land-concentrated customary assets, for example, agribusiness and forestry. **Surbhi Agrawal (2016)**, Commonplace improvement has acquired in general thought, especially among emerging nations, and it is crucial for a nation like India. **Ali, N., and Akhtar, Z. (1999)**. The

audit means to explore the effect of word related pressure and various leveled climate on work satisfaction of bosses and fashioners working in Indian Oil Organization Confined, Mathura, India. **Hackman, J. R., and Oldham, G. R. (1976)**. A model is recommended that decides the conditions under which individuals will end up being inside enlivened to perform effectively on their positions. Review of writing on issues of corporate work . **Lodahl, T. M., and Kejner, M. (1965)**. The model and set hypotheses were taken a stab at using essential condition showing assessment. The results exhibited that work commitment emphatically and basically impacts work satisfaction and legitimate liability. **Schneider, B., Hanges, P. J., Smith, D. B., and Salvaggio, A. N. (2003)**. In any case, our results should be unraveled thinking about a couple of obstructions.

Research Methodology

This exploration Descriptive Statistical Analysis Involves Collecting, Interpreting, Analyzing, And Summarizing Data To Present Them In The Form Of Charts, Graphs, And Tables. Rather Than Drawing Conclusions, It Simply Makes The Complex Data Easy To Read And Understand. The standard deviation (s or SD) is the average amount of variability in dataset. It represents on average, how far each score lies from the mean of tribal development . Quantitative exploration gives mathematical information or information that can be changed into usable measurements. It very well may be utilized to affirm speculations and theories about a peculiarity or to foresee future events. Techniques for quantitative assessment incorporate polls, reviews and testing. It is utilized to measure ways of behaving, perspectives, sentiments, and other characterized factors. Also, it gives knowledge into the issue by fostering a grasping in view of mathematical information examination. The standard deviation (s or SD) is the typical measure of changeability in dataset. In this research , Inferential statistics are divided into two categories: 1. **Hypothesis testing**. 2. **Regression analysis**.

Standardize Scale For Data Collection

Scale of Indian human development survey – II as per national council of applied economic research (NCAER) is used for data collection and analysis . “NATIONAL COUNCIL OF APPLIED ECONOMIC RESEARCH 08 December 2020” . Scale of Self made standardized questionnaire is used for data collection (3 point likert scale)

Delimitation

The work is delimited to seven blocks under north 24 paraganas in west Bengal on Mundari tribal groups of **Bagdah , Bongaon , Giaghata , Swarupnagar , Minakhan , Sandeshkhali –II , and Hingaljanj** block in north 24 paraganas , west Bengal . In seven blocks only 1200 mundari family has been taken for survey.

Analysis And Interpretation

The ancestral construction which should be straightforward and inflexible, has noticed penetrance of a few outside components into their way of life which is moving them more towards an edified at this point complex society. In the Indian sub-landmass, because of previously existing variety, there are various compartments of society like religion, economy, power, legislative issues and so on which ranges through "different societies" to find where they could be adjusted with their local area.

H₀₁ Social participation has no impact on Mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Benga

Statement	Agree (%)	Neutral(%)	Disagree(%)
Mundari sub-caste has a phobia on social participation	72.32	15.36	12.32
Mundari community never belong to cultural society	71.21	14.58	14.21
Mundari workars are involved in social participation	21.21	6.43	72.36
Mundari community involved in ICDS programme	23.21	13.58	63.21
Mundari community involved in SSK education policy	32.21	2.58	65.21

Fig : Social Participation Of Mundari Tribal Groups

Table for Regression Statistics

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.988973
R Square	0.978068
Adjusted R Square	0.970758
Standard Error	5.060925
Observations	5

Anova analysis table

ANOVA	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	3426.718	3426.718	133.7884	0.001388
Residual	3	76.83889	25.61296		
Total	4	3503.557			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	95.69407	4.89721	19.54053	0.00029	80.10896	111.2792	80.10896	111.2792
Agree (%)	-1.14081	0.098629	-11.5667	0.001388	1.45469	0.82693	1.45469	0.82693

One such shift is through religion, which tracks down additional intense adherents among the socially underestimated tribals, by building contacts with them. This perhaps actuated forcibly by catching their region or by acknowledgment by means of expanding exchange and invasion into their spaces.

H₀₂ There is no relation between health and medical drawback and development of mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal

Statement	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
Mundari community conscious about health education	21.32	25.47	53.21
Mundari community conscious about modern medical treatment	13.21	11.58	75.21
Helthy food is available in Mundari society	24.32	6.36	69.32
Mundari community believe on ancient medicinal plant	71.32	15.47	13.21
Mundari community believe on superstition about health check up	65.32	13.47	21.21

Fig : health and medical drawbacks of mundari tribal groups

Anova analysis table

ANOVA	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	2940.71	2940.71	44.7562	0.006813
Residual	3	197.1153	65.7051		
Total	4	3137.826			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	85.59815	6.885878	12.43097	0.001122	63.68421	107.5121	63.68421	107.5121
Agree (%)	-1.00174	0.149737	-6.690013	0.006813	-1.47827	-0.52521	-1.47827	-0.52521

The ancestral networks are more helpless to strict transformations due to one or the other shunning by their own local area individuals or absence of education and powerlessness to take ready choices. the majority of the Kharias took to Mundari and had the option to acquire instructive open doors through the rural evangelists.

H₀₃ There is no relation between Agro-economical Crisis and Social Status of mundari tribal groups of various blocks in North 24 Paraganas , West Bengal

Statement	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
Mundari community need agricultural education	76.32	0.47	23.21
The economy of Mundari sub-caste depend on agricultur	91.21	5.58	3.21
Male Mundari community very much involved in agricultur	72.32	6.36	21.32
Per capita income is sufficient of Mundari community	12.32	14.47	73.21
Mundari community need other job	56.32	22.36	21.32

Fig : Agro-Economical Crisis Of Mundari Tribal Groups

Anova analysis table

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	2570.219	2570.219	38.66392	0.008385
Residual	3	199.4277	66.47589		
Total	4	2769.647			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	80.12383	9.074464	8.829594	0.003062	51.24484	109.0028	51.24484	109.0028
Agree (%)	-0.83746	0.134683	-6.218035	0.008385	-1.26609	-0.40884	-1.26609	-0.40884

They were the ones who knew about the allowances, grants and reservations gave to them, and to which they promptly acknowledged and thus advanced toward the metropolitan regions. Such tribals on movement got socially segregated from their brethren in the provincial regions and fostered a better approach for living. Thus, the differentials made as such separated one clan into two sections as the significant value 00.00852. Essentially, in one district on the off chance that the individuals from a clan convert to at least two strict groups, there is a socio-social hindrance made between them which limits their cooperation and makes pressure.

The probability of obtaining the sample result is Null Hypothesis were true (the p value) is based on two considerations: relationship strength and sample size. Reasonable judgments about whether a sample relationship is statistically significant can often be made by quickly considering these two factors. Statistical significance is not the same as relationship strength or importance. In this research , the P-value is less than the α , there should be a REJECTION of the null hypothesis in favour of the alternate hypothesis on Mundari Social Participation , Mundari Health And Medical , Mundari Agro- Economical aspects as a research domain of Bagdah , Bongaon , Giaghata , Swarupnagar , Minakhan , Sandeshkhali –II , and Hingalganj block in north 24 paraganas , west Bengal ..

Findings Of Research

The major ancestral issues of Mundari , incorporate land-distance, obligation, personality emergencies, unfortunate proficiency and training, joblessness, relocation and recovery, and absence of wellbeing, nourishment and cleanliness. These are joined by the lacunae in the approach making, execution and work force abilities and preparing of the public authority divisions who are conveyed in the ancestral regions to grasp their requirements and satisfy their obligations as requested by the public authority. The central variables answerable for the issues of the clans are widespread urbanization and industrialization in the ancestral regions, the socio-social elements, backwoods strategy and tribals, and the traditionalism and hesitance to change of the tribals. The different issues that are to be tended to by the public authority incorporates . in the block of **Bagdah , Bongaon , Giaghata , Swarupnagar , Minakhan , Sandeshkhali –II , and Hingalganj** in north 24 paraganas , west Bengal . Schooling Low enrolment, high quitters, hole in training among STs and different gatherings, distance of schools, unfortunate business, non-accessibility of educators, language and social obstructions, absence of professional preparation and so forth. Wellbeing: Insufficient framework, low inoculation, hunger, loss of conventional food, lacking inclusion of pregnant moms, distance of regions prompting high IMR, MMR among tribals, non-accessibility of safe drinking water, high occurrence of Jungle fever, Sickle Cell Frailty, GED, URTI, Fluorosis and so forth. Business: Absence of abilities, preparing valuable open doors, and in reverse and forward linkages-agribusiness exercises, deficient network, timberland corruption, absence of water system and market linkages prompting joblessness, low pay from customary occupations and absence of backwoods variety. Culture: Absence of mindfulness and protection of ancestral culture, interact with scholarly society, framework or instrument, market linkage to advance ancestral art and nonappearance of ancestral exhibition halls on vacationer guides of the States prompting loss of conventional games, specialties, meds, and restorative practices, feeling of estrangement, loss of feeling of pride over ancestral culture and loss of legacy, cooking and customary food sources in **Bagdah , Bongaon , Giaghata , Swarupnagar , Minakhan , Sandeshkhali – II , and Hingalganj** block in north 24 paraganas , west Bengal .

Recommendations Of Research

The significant plans and plans of progress for ancestral improvement incorporates: Protection cum-advancement , plans including the plan of Improvement of Especially Weak Ancestral Gatherings (PVTGs), Focal Area Plans , which incorporates plans connected with schooling, grant to poor ST understudies, upliftment of young ladies, professional preparation, award in-help to deliberate associations, least help value (MSP) for tribals, funding plans, mass training and social plans and so on. Other than these are the Public Booked Clans Money and Advancement Company , including sub-plans like Adivasi Mahila Sashaktikaran Yojana (AMSY), Term Advance Plan, Miniature Credit Plan, Adivasi Shiksha Rinn Yojana, Ancestral Woodland Inhabitants Strengthening Plan, and Help to TRIFED empanelled craftsmans. The Block Awards include: Extraordinary Focal Help to Ancestral Sub-plan (SCA to TSP) and Award under Article 275(1) of the setting of mundari advancement in north 24 paraganas , west Bengal and as well as populational viewpoint

ancestral examination of mundari local area of **Bagdah, Bongaon, Giaghata, Swarupnagar, Minakhan, Sandeshkhali –II, and Hingalganj** block in north 24 paraganas, west Bengal.

Conclusion

The term clan munda however an ordinary word in the majority of the educational elements of the present world, incredibly hasn't found a widespread definition till date even following quite a while of study and exploration in 24 north paraganas . The issue isn't absence of devotion or interest, yet the world is so different and dynamic to oblige unique arrangements of human populaces into one form. For instance, the clans call themselves by names which partner them to their property and environmental elements; they announce themselves to be the primary occupants of their territory, or the "principal people". This attestation however misses the mark in the sacred structure of characterizing the clans in view of their financial status in contrast with the other sub-populaces of the country. The Indian Constitution characterizes them under the established term, "the Booked Clans", of **Bagdah, Bongaon, Giaghata, Swarupnagar, Minakhan, Sandeshkhali –II, and Hingalganj** block in north 24 paraganas , west Bengal . which effectively designates specific networks, where enrollment is obtained by birth, for the advantages that the public authority gives them the express point of carrying them at standard with different networks of the country. The Assistance of Familial Issues was made to guarantee an attracted and created strategy for dealing with the improvement of booked clans in a planned and coordinated way. The edifying necessities of familial kids are on an exceptionally fundamental level watched out for through non-government funded schools called ashram schools. There are 892 mostly upheld ashram schools spread the nation over. These give boarding and housing working environments to youngsters in genetic regions until they complete their optional arrangement. Adjacent to these, the division has similarly begun 197 Eklavya Model Non-state funded schools on the lines of KGBVs and Navodaya Vidyalayas. There is little consistency in the association of ashram schools, thought of basic locales or nature of foundation across the states. While the Help of Ancestral Issues gives the assets for the progression of inns, the tasks and standard working of these lodgings are done by the particular state overseeing bodies or alliance regions. Plans of bosses and educators shift as per school associations. Lodgings are in some cases oversaw by non-government relationship with help awards from the working environment. By a wide margin a large portion of the tribal schools are not charming to least guidelines.

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